

Electromagnetic Wave Functions of CMB and Schwarzschild Space-Time

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Abstract: In the general relativity theory, we find electro-magnetic wave functions of Cosmic Microwave Background and Schwarzschild space-time. Specially, this article is that electromagnetic wave equations are treated by gauge fixing equations in Robertson-Walker space-time and Schwarzschild space-time.

Keywords: General relativity theory, Electro-magnetic wave equations; Electromagnetic wave functions; Cosmic Microwave Background; Schwarzschild space-time

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INTRODUCTION

In the general relativity theory, our article's aim is that we find electro-magnetic wave equations and functions by gauge fixing equations in Robertson-Walker space-time and Schwarzschild space-time.

At first, Electro-magnetic field equations are in general relativity theory

$$F^{\mu\nu}{}_{;\nu} = \frac{4\pi}{c} j^{\mu} \quad (1)$$

$$F_{\mu\nu;\lambda} + F_{\nu\lambda;\mu} + F_{\lambda\mu;\nu} = 0 \quad (2)$$

The electro-magnetic field is

$$F_{\mu\nu} = A_{\nu;\mu} - A_{\mu;\nu} = \frac{\partial A_{\nu}}{\partial x^{\mu}} - \frac{\partial A_{\mu}}{\partial x^{\nu}} \quad (3)$$

The gauge fixing equation in general relativity theory

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\mu}{}_{;\mu} &= \frac{\partial A^{\mu}}{\partial x^{\mu}} + \Gamma^{\mu}{}_{\mu\rho} A^{\rho} \\ \rightarrow \partial_{\mu} (A^{\mu} + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\nu} \Lambda) + \Gamma^{\mu}{}_{\mu\rho} (A^{\rho} + \partial^{\rho} \Lambda) \\ &= \partial_{\mu} (A^{\mu} + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\nu} \Lambda) + \Gamma^{\mu}{}_{\mu\rho} (A^{\rho} + g^{\rho\sigma} \partial_{\sigma} \Lambda) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

1. ELECTRO-MAGNETIC WAVE EQUATION IN ROBERTSON-WALKER SPACE-TIME

Because the gauge fixing equation is the electro-magnetic wave equation, the electro-magnetic wave equation is in Robertson-Walker space-time.

The Robertson-Walker solution is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t) \left[\frac{dr^2}{1-kr^2} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right] \quad (5)$$

In this time, 2-dimensional solution is

$$d\Omega = 0$$

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t) \frac{dr^2}{1-kr^2} \quad (6)$$

The gauge fixing equation is in 2-dimensional solution

$$\partial_\mu (A^\mu + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \Lambda) + \Gamma^\mu_{\mu\rho} (A^\rho + g^{\rho\sigma} \partial_\sigma \Lambda)$$

$$= \partial_\mu A^\mu + \Gamma^1_{10} A^0 + \Gamma^1_{11} A^1 + \partial_\mu g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \Lambda + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \partial_\nu \Lambda + \Gamma^1_{10} g^{00} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial t} + \Gamma^1_{11} g^{11} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial r} \quad (7)$$

Hence, we can find electro-magnetic wave equation in 2-dimentional Robertson-Walker space-time.

$$\partial_\mu g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu (\sin\Phi) + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \partial_\nu (\sin\Phi) + \Gamma^1_{10} g^{00} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\sin\Phi) + \Gamma^1_{11} g^{11} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (\sin\Phi)$$

$$= \left[\frac{-2kr}{\Omega^2(t)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} + \frac{1-kr^2}{\Omega^2(t)} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} - \frac{\dot{\Omega}}{c\Omega} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \frac{kr}{\Omega^2(t)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right] \sin\Phi = 0$$

$$\Gamma^1_{10} = \frac{\dot{\Omega}}{c\Omega}, \quad \Gamma^1_{11} = \frac{kr}{1-kr^2} \quad (8)$$

In this time, we can think the shape of electro-magnetic wave function from 2-dimentional Robertson-Walker space-time. In this case, light is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t) \frac{dr^2}{1-kr^2} = 0$$

$$\int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} = \frac{1}{c} \int \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1-kr^2}} \quad (9)$$

Hence, electro-magnetic wave function is in 2-dimentional Robertson-Walker space-time-

$$\vec{E} = \vec{E}_0 \sin\Phi, \vec{B} = \vec{B}_0 \sin\Phi$$

$$\Phi = \omega_0 \left[\int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} - \frac{1}{c} \int \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1-kr^2}} \right]$$

i) $k = 1, \Phi = \omega_0 \left[\int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} - \frac{1}{c} \sin^{-1} r \right]$

ii) $k = 0, \Phi = \omega_0 \left[\int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} - \frac{1}{c} r \right]$

iii) $k = -1, \Phi = \omega_0 \left[\int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} - \frac{1}{c} \sinh^{-1} r \right] \quad (10)$

The electro-magnetic wave equation-Eq(8) is satisfied by the electro-magnetic wave function-Eq(10).

2. ELECTRO-MAGNETIC WAVE EQUATION IN SCHWARZSCHILD SPACE-TIME

Because the gauge fixing equation is the electro-magnetic wave equation, the electro-magnetic wave equation is in Schwarzschild space-time.

The Schwarzschild solution is

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left[\frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right] \quad (11)$$

In this time, 2-dimensional solution is

$$d\Omega = 0$$

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \quad (12)$$

The gauge fixing equation is in 2-dimensional solution

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_\mu (A^\mu + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \Lambda) + \Gamma^\mu_{\mu\rho} (A^\rho + g^{\rho\sigma} \partial_\sigma \Lambda) \\ &= \partial_\mu A^\mu + \Gamma^0_{01} A^1 + \Gamma^1_{11} A^1 + \partial_\mu g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \Lambda + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \partial_\nu \Lambda + \Gamma^0_{01} g^{11} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial r} + \Gamma^1_{11} g^{11} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial r} \\ &= \partial_\mu A^\mu + \partial_\mu g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \Lambda + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \partial_\nu \Lambda \\ \Gamma^0_{01} &= \frac{GM}{r^2 c^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}, \quad \Gamma^1_{11} = -\frac{GM}{r^2 c^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Hence, we can find electro-magnetic wave equation in 2-dimentional Schwarzschild space-time.

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_\mu g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu (\sin\Phi) + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \partial_\nu (\sin\Phi) \\ &= \left[\frac{2GM}{r^2 c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} \right] \sin\Phi = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

In this time, we can think the shape of electro-magnetic wave function from 2-dimentional Schwarzschild space-time. In this case, light is

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} = 0$$

$$t = \frac{1}{c} \int \frac{dr}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} = \frac{r}{c} + \frac{2GM}{c^3} \ln \left| r - \frac{2GM}{c^2} \right| \quad (15)$$

Hence, electro-magnetic wave function is in 2-dimentional Schwarzschild space-time-

$$\vec{E} = \vec{E}_0 \sin\Phi, \vec{B} = \vec{B}_0 \sin\Phi$$

$$\Phi = \omega_0 \left[t - \frac{r}{c} - \frac{2GM}{c^3} \ln \left| r - \frac{2GM}{c^2} \right| \right] \quad (16)$$

The electro-magnetic wave equation-Eq(14) is satisfied by the electro-magnetic wave function-Eq(16).

3. CONCLUSION

We find the electro-magnetic wave (CMB) equation and function in Robertson-Walker space-time.
We find the electro-magnetic wave equation and function in Schwarzschild space-time.

REFERENCES

- [1] S.Yi, "Electromagnetic Field Equation and Lorentz Gauge in Rindler space-time", The African review of physics,**11**,33(2016)-INSPIRE-HEP
- [2] S.Yi, "Electromagnetic Wave Function and Equation, Lorentz Force in Rindler space-time", International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science,**5**,9(2018)
- [3] S. Weinberg, Gravitation and Cosmology(John wiley & Sons,Inc,1972)
- [4] W. Rindler, Am.J.Phys.**34**.1174(1966)
- [5] P. Bergman, Introduction to the Theory of Relativity (Dover Pub. Co.,Inc., New York,1976),Chapter V
- [6] C. Misner, K. Thorne and J. Wheeler, Gravitation(W.H.Freedman & Co.,1973)
- [7] S. Hawking and G. Ellis, The Large Scale Structure of Space-Time(Cam-bridge University Press,1973)
- [8] R. Adler, M. Bazin and M. Schiffer, Introduction to General Relativity(McGraw-Hill,Inc.,1965)
- [9] A. Miller, Albert Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity(Addison-Wesley Publishing Co., Inc., 1981)
- [10] W. Rindler, Special Relativity(2nd ed., Oliver and Boyd, Edinburg,1966)
- [11] Massimo Pauri, Michele Vallisner, "Marzke-Wheeler coordinates for accelerated observers in special relativity":Arxiv:gr-qc/0006095(2000)
- [12] A. Einstein, "Zur Elektrodynamik bewegter K"orper", Annalen der Physik. 17:891(1905)

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